

From a Contemplative to a Critical Attitude: Lukács, Foucault, and the Partisanship of Critical Theory

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Abstract: The objective of critical theory is to advocate for emancipatory social transformation. The partisanship of contemporary critical theory has become increasingly unclear over time, however. This article proposes to restore critical theory's alignment with ongoing social struggles, rather than grounding it in normative social theory. To revive critical theory's partisan orientation, I draw on Georg Lukács' critique of reification. I argue that Lukács' dialectical relationship between reification and the proletarian standpoint provides the paradigmatic model for emancipatory social critique. In addition, I suggest that Michel Foucault's explorations of power, resistance, and the "critical attitude" are consistent with Lukács' model of partisan critique. Returning to Lukács' assessment of the impediment of militant action caused by reification, this paper advocates for a model of social critique that prioritizes concrete social struggles. The comparison of Lukács and Foucault calls for an examination of contemporary social struggles as the primary point of orientation for social critique. Thus, the partisanship of critical theory not only aims to promote emancipatory politics, but is also necessary in order for theory to be critical at all.

Keywords: reification, partisanship, critical theory, Georg Lukács, Michel Foucault

In other words, it is not up to an intellectual to say: "Rebel, go and make a revolution!" The intellectual work which I carry out consists in showing in some way how fragile those things are which we take as evidence. Consequently, my work, or if you like my activity as a militant, is to be part of a movement or a group which can operate from within this space—a space which I believe is free and from which we can liberate.¹

— Michel Foucault

What makes critical theory “critical” is its commitment to emancipatory social transformation. By origin, critical theories embrace the Marxist commitment to initiating, advancing, or clarifying the emancipatory struggle of subordinate social classes, and, by extension, the emancipation of society as a whole. Over time, however, it has become increasingly unclear to whom, if anyone, this “partisanship” of contemporary critical theory refers. The Marxist thinkers who—directly or indirectly—inspired the critical theory of the Frankfurt School, such as Georg Lukács, Rosa Luxemburg, Karl Korsch, and Anton Pannekoek,² believed that their theoretical work was intertwined with the ongoing struggle of the working class for the betterment of society. However, the failure of the Council Communist revolutions in Western and Central Europe around 1920 shook the Marxist belief in the viability of a successful proletarian revolution. These events led to Lukács’ seminal essay on reification in *History and Class Consciousness* (1923) and the founding of the Frankfurt Institute for Social Research in the same year. Increasingly, critical theorists had to account for what Lukács called the “ideological crisis of the proletariat” to explain what was blocking the “objective possibility” of class consciousness.³ Thus, early critical theory grew out of the fact that the link between economic development and social transformation that Marx had envisaged was less obvious than expected. To the extent that capitalism did not immediately produce its own gravediggers, it was deemed that the task of critical theory should be to help put the shovels in the hands of the proletariat.

With the imminent rise of fascism, however, the program of critical theory evolved from such partisanship with the working class to the espousal of a gloomy view of late capitalist society. Consequently, the critical theorists of the Frankfurt School came to the conclusion that “critique could not be directly grounded in the praxis or consciousness of the class that Marx had assigned the historical role of incipient universal class.”⁴ Instead, theorists like Theodor Adorno and Max Horkheimer resorted to exposing the ideological underpinnings of the existing state of affairs without explicitly engaging in political struggle.⁵

Against subsequent efforts to re-ground critical theory in a normative theory of society, this paper argues that critical theory’s “partisanship” with actual social struggles must be re-established in order to uphold its emancipatory commitment. By partisanship, I do not refer to the active participation in or membership of political organization per se. Rather, I want to make a more methodological point. I contend that, insofar as theories of social emancipation do not give primacy to forms of struggle that already exist immanent to society, they risk becoming indistinguishable from hermetic metaphysical Spielereien or a Kantian empty ought. “Partisanship,” in this sense, refers to the primacy of critical attitudes and practices in society to establish what has been called the “unity of theory and praxis,” rather than a “strong and sometimes blind adherence to a particular party, faction, cause, or person,” as Merriam-Webster defines it.⁶ Put differently, the “partisanship” I have in mind corresponds to the “problem of political consciousness” central to the Lukácsian paradigm that has become central to critical theory after the Second World War. Indeed, Hauke

Brunkhorst has argued that “if one understands Lukacs’ undertaking [...] as a paradigm in Kuhn’s sense which posits ‘the problem to be solved,’” then “there are two and only two problems which open onto solvable puzzles [...]. These two central problem areas are: (1) the problem of reification (and rationalization),

(2) the problem of class consciousness (and of the unity of theory and praxis).”⁷ Insofar as critical theory strives to question reified social forms on grounds that are immanent to society, it needs to adhere to concrete emancipatory demands within society to ground social critique.⁸ Hence, for theory to remain practically committed to emancipation, it must contribute to existing struggles in society and move beyond the contemplative confines of the “Grand Hotel Abyss,” as Lukács reproachfully described the attitude of his colleagues in Frankfurt.

To redevelop such “partisanship,” I return to Lukács’ dialectic between reification and the standpoint of the proletariat. Beyond the excavation of Lukács’ model, I will argue—perhaps surprisingly⁹—that Michel Foucault’s work on power, resistance, and “the critical attitude” comes close to Lukács’ paradigmatic model for critical theory. I argue that Foucault’s genealogical method and Lukács’ dialectical model have a similar aim: to undo reification by referring to the transformative force of the struggles of subordinated social groups. As Jürgen Habermas has argued, Foucault’s genealogical emphasis on “disqualified popular knowledge” can be read in analogy to “the privileged possibilities of knowledge” identified by Lukács in the “perspective of experience that had arisen with the position of the wage-laborer in the process of production.”¹⁰ Similarly, Gilles Deleuze has connected Foucault’s interest in subjectivation and forms and struggle to “Lukács, whose *History and Class Consciousness* was already raising questions to do with a new subjectivity.”¹¹ Taking seriously Lukács’ reflection on the impediment of militant action caused by reification, I argue that social critique must give concrete social struggles a primary role in critiquing the self-evidence of reification. Insofar as social theory purports to be critical, it needs to nourish some connection to political praxis, precisely because praxis is a necessary condition for acquiring the requisite knowledge and insight to feed and orient the emancipatory outlook of critical theory beyond reification.

First, I return to Lukács’ critique of reification and its grounding in the standpoint of working-class struggle (I). I then explain the ways in which Frankfurt School critical theory moved on from Lukács’ partisanship. I revisit how Horkheimer’s reversal of the relationship between theory and practice developed into the pessimism he shared with Adorno after the Second World War (II). Subsequently, I discuss how their position laid the groundwork for the reconstructive proceduralism of Habermas and Honneth (III). I then argue that Foucault’s emphasis on the correlation between power and resistance takes up the paradigmatic relationship between reification and political consciousness in a non-dialectical model (IV). Next, I show how Foucault links social critique to

subjects of social transformation beyond traditional mass movements (V). Finally, I conclude that the Lukácsian paradigm finds a parallel in the Foucauldian approach to power and resistance, which provides a contemporaneous answer to the problem of the unity of theory and praxis central to critical theory.

I. LUKÁCS' CRITIQUE OF CONTEMPLATION

Critical theory's commitment to emancipation originates from the socialist movement's struggle for the emancipation of the working class. The eleventh of Marx's "Theses on Feuerbach" aptly articulates its central principle: "Philosophers have hitherto only interpreted the world in various ways; the point is to change it."¹² In *History and Class Consciousness*, Lukács famously repeats that mere theoretical contemplation reifies the capitalist social structure rather than challenging it. Even before participating in the Hungarian Council Republic of 1919, Lukács opposed an understanding of "the intellectual force of the 'intellectual workers' as complementary to progress."¹³ On the contrary, he asserts that "the position arrived at by the theoretician only after arduous intellectual work is one which the proletariat, precisely because he belongs to the proletariat, already and always occupies."¹⁴ Lukács' *History and Class Consciousness* (1923) marks a turning point in Marxist theorizing, however. Its reflection on reification transcends the opportunism of the dominant intellectual currents within the socialist movement by observing that the capitalist form of life leads individuals to adapt their behavior to its seemingly necessary laws, leading to the reification of society into a quasi-necessary "second nature."¹⁵ The point of Lukács' intervention was to show how the subjective attitudes provoked by capitalism prevent attainment of the class consciousness necessary for revolutionary change. More precisely, Lukács argues that in capitalism, the "commodity form" becomes the "form of objectivity" of all social relations. As the rationality emerging from commodity production and exchange provokes a contemplative, calculative stance, it transforms the way subjects relate to themselves, others, society, and the material world within and beyond the economy. According to Lukács, then, this form of objectivity creates a "social form" conditioned by the categories of validity emerging from the capitalist economy.¹⁶ Hence, Lukács argues that the passive, contemplative disposition produced by capitalist rationality leads to the reification of all capitalist social relations.

Lukács discusses the causes and effects of the contemplative attitude most explicitly in relation to the situation of the worker. He argues that "with the increasing rationalization and mechanization of the work process, the activity of the worker loses more and more of its character as an activity and becomes a contemplative stance."¹⁷ It is not only on the factory floor that individuals adopt a contemplative attitude, however. Beyond the worker's integration into capitalist production, Lukács points to the ubiquity of the contemplative attitude in other social spheres. He suggests that the individual becomes "a spectator" of society in which "modern administration and law assume the character of the factory floor," leading to a "contemplative attitude towards the

functioning of his [sic] own objectified and objectified abilities.”¹⁸ Moreover, Lukács draws a comparison between the passive role of the worker in the factory and “the completely mechanized, ‘mindless’ way of working of the lower bureaucracy which comes extraordinarily close to mere machine operation [...] surpassing the latter in dullness and uniformity. But also [...] an increasing formal-rationalistic treatment of all questions [...] to which bureaucratic activity pertains.”¹⁹ Hence, Lukács argues, the “contemplative relation” typical of labor’s Taylorization extends beyond the commodification of labor to the fields of state administration and the judiciary. In all these cases, “thought proceeds naively” and “praxis appears to be consistently subordinated to the theory of contemplation.”²⁰ As a result, people experience society as a whole as being structured “independently of consciousness and uninfluenced by human activity, thus revealing itself to be a ready-made (fertig) closed system.”²¹

For Lukács’ diagnosis of reification, the problem of the unity of theory and praxis is the central point of reference. This is showcased by his reflections on the “contemplative attitude” that emerges from the commodity form. According to Lukács, both the bourgeois theorization of society, ethics, culture, and science, and everyday social practice are characterized by a passive contemplation of the existing “laws” of capitalist society. By adopting a contemplative attitude towards their environment, individuals adapt their practices in order to survive within the existing social order, hence reifying it. As a result, existing social relations manifest themselves as a thing-like given for the theorist, too. Indeed, Lukács suggests that “this world can only be understood” if one adopts “the theoretical form of ‘eternal laws of nature,’ that is, when it acquires an alien rationality that is completely uninfluenced by and impenetrable to the individual’s possibilities of action, when the human [der Mensch] relates purely contemplatively and fatalistically towards it.”²² As a result, the contemplative attitude subordinates subjective consciousness to the rationality of capitalism:

Consciousness either becomes a completely passive spectator of a law-like movement of things in which it cannot intervene under any circumstances, or it regards itself as a power that is able to master the intrinsically senseless movement of things according to its own—subjective—will.²³

To prove his point, Lukács lengthily reflects on the contemplative character of modern philosophy, Kant’s transcendental philosophy being his main example. According to him, transcendental philosophy reifies capitalist culture into a form of thing-like facticity. Lukács lengthily argues that “modern critical philosophy springs from the reified structure of consciousness,”²⁴ and that transcendental philosophy approaches the world “as ‘necessary,’ i.e., as visible in or ‘created’ by the forms themselves.”²⁵ As a result, transcendental philosophy fails “to overcome the reified disintegration of the subject and the—likewise reified—

rigidity and impenetrability of its objects.”²⁶ Kant’s ethics, for instance, “becomes purely formal and lacking in content,” hence reifying the capitalist status quo.²⁷ Put shortly, modern philosophy only contemplates the rational forms of thought, thereby remaining stuck in the reified categories of modern capitalist life.

In sum, Lukács characterizes the attitude of capitalist subjects as an effort to adapt their behavior to conform to the laws of the economy and society. Accordingly, individuals are ill positioned to recognize that these “systems” are human constructs that can be challenged and transformed. In short, the contemplative attitude typical of the capitalist form of life reifies the status quo and blocks critique and political action.²⁸

However, Lukács’ diagnosis does not necessarily imply a pessimistic conclusion. On the contrary: Lukács adopts a strongly partisan stance—which is increasingly partisan in the literal sense—claiming that the proletariat is the class that is, *per se*, best positioned to break through the reification of society. Although the contemplative attitude explains why capitalism does not necessarily create its own gravediggers, Lukács suggests that an “objective possibility” of revolutionary transformation still persists. He argues that only the class consciousness of the proletariat, when it has become practical, possesses this transforming ability. Every contemplative, merely cognitive attitude ultimately stands in a twofold relation to its object, and the simple transplantation of the structure discerned here into any other attitude than the action of the proletariat [...] would bring about a new conceptual mythology, a regression to the standpoint of classical philosophy refuted by Marx.²⁹

From his first engagement with the communist movement to *History and Class Consciousness*, Lukács theorizes this possibility by combining elements of Rosa Luxemburg’s spontaneist understanding of mass action, ultra-leftist reflections on worker’s councils, and an increasing emphasis on a vanguard Leninist party.³⁰ Over the course of the essays published in the book, however, Lukács increasingly privileges a Leninist model over a Luxemburgian one, arguing in the final essay that “the unconditional absorption of the total personality in the praxis of the movement, was the only possible way of bringing about an authentic freedom,”³¹ while dismissing Luxemburg’s emphasis on mass spontaneity as “still infected with Utopianism.”³² In the midst of working-class organization during the Hungarian Council Republic and his underground exile in Vienna, however, Lukács continued to express ultra-left tendencies within the communist movement, searching for the appropriate tactics to continue the failed council revolutions in Central Europe.³³ Even after the publication of his apologetic book on Lenin (1924), he continued to argue for partly non-Leninist tactics in his 1926 “Blum Theses.”³⁴ It should also be noted that after the failure of the Blum Theses, followed by one of the many self-critiques produced by Lukács and a retreat from party activities, his writings on literature during the early 1930s are characterized by a partisanship in the most narrow, Bolshevik

sense. Being sent on a propagandist mission from Moscow to Berlin in the early 1930s, Lukács writes revisionist essays in the *Linkskurve* that reproach spontaneist politics³⁵ in favor of a partisanship [Parteilichkeit] with the Leninist party, doubling down on his Lenin book of 1924. There, he claims that “correct dialectical depiction and literary portrayal of reality presupposes the partisanship of the writer,” “partisanship for the class that is the bearer of historical progress in our period: for the proletariat, and specifically for that ‘section of the working-class party,’ the Communists.”³⁶

The flux between vanguardist, spontaneist, and parliamentarist tactics underlines Lukács’ suggestion that the appropriate communist tactics are conditioned by concrete historical circumstances.³⁷ For the early Lukács, the critique of capitalism only makes sense insofar as it is embedded in the fluctuating tactical challenges of the ongoing social struggle. Although Lukács opts for a Leninist model of partisanship towards the end of *History and Class Consciousness*, this organizational strategy is a second-order question with regards to the partisanship central to this paper. In first instance, Lukács’ approach is characterized by a directedness of his theory towards the proletarian struggle he seeks to catalyze. Moreover, these strategic concerns are both immanent to society and capable of moving beyond the contemplation of self-evident “facts.” Without taking into account its social position, theory can only reproduce the reification of the existing social order. Approaching organization as “the form of mediation between theory and practice,”³⁸ and arguing for “a form of struggle in which the initiative lies wholly with the proletariat”³⁹ Lukács suggests that “only a theory which is able to influence facts fruitfully and, in turn, to profit from the facts, is truly adequate.”⁴⁰ Understanding his critique of reification against the backdrop of organizational and tactical concerns, critique is for Lukács a deeply partisan intellectual enterprise that sides with the struggles and needs of the proletariat. In the following, I will trace the decline of this model within Frankfurt School critical theory.

II. HORKHEIMER’S CRITICAL PARTISANSHIP

Even after the failure of the Hungarian Council Communist Republic, Lukács continued to believe that the working class was well placed to overcome the contemplative attitude fostered by capitalism. In German Marxist circles, however, the failure of the council republics in Central Europe hampered the relationship between theory and political practice. While Lukács was directly involved in political organization, the institutionalization of Frankfurt School critical theory took place while its members no longer perceived there to be a well-organized labor movement to support. Nevertheless, Lukács’ diagnosis of reification remained crucial to the development of the Frankfurt School’s critical theory. For both, Marx’s philosophical and political reflections continued to be the primary sources for understanding the present,⁴¹ moving beyond the economic and deterministic varieties of Marxism. Finally, both combined

Marx's diagnosis of capitalism with a variety of other insights to explain why the proletariat did not overthrow capitalism as expected, but instead became increasingly reactionary. Finally, Lukács' diagnosis of reification as blockage of political action became all the more relevant after the totale Verblendungszusammenhang of postwar late capitalism achieved full force.

By the 1930s, however, the normative claims of critical theory were still aligned with those well established by the socialist movement. In his programmatic text "Traditionelle und kritische Theorie," Max Horkheimer, one of the Frankfurt School's key figures, argues that "the theoretician and his specific object are seen as forming a dynamic unity with the oppressed class, so that his presentation of societal contradictions is not merely an expression of the concrete historical situation but also a force within it to stimulate change."⁴² As such, the position of early critical theory is comparable to that of Lukács, although the members of the Frankfurt School were fellow travelers of working-class uprisings rather than participants in them. Nevertheless, Axel Honneth is right to claim that in the 1930s, for the Frankfurt School, "the historical evidence of social class struggles seemed to demonstrate clearly the existence of a social movement led by moral principles."⁴³ The pressing question was not whether the struggle against capitalism is justified, but rather how a revolutionary subjectivity could emerge to bring about social change. In his 1937 essay "Philosophy and Critical Theory," written as a counterpoint to Horkheimer's programmatic piece, Herbert Marcuse poses precisely this question: "what if the forces that were to bring about the transformation are suppressed and appear to be defeated?"⁴⁴

Horkheimer assigns the theorist a fundamental role in preventing the latter scenario. Like Lukács, he identifies resistance to mere contemplation as a defining characteristic of critical theory. He elaborates the contemplative quality of "traditional theory," which according to Horkheimer consists of hypothetical sets of propositions about facts, events, or experiences, idealizes a type of theory that creates a purely mathematical system of symbols. This mechanistic view of the world—on which traditional theory's claim to scientific neutrality and objectivity is based—means that "the real social function of science is not made manifest."⁴⁵ Instead, Horkheimer argues, the mathematization of knowledge limits traditional theories to instrumentally manipulating nature in the function of existing socio-economic mechanisms:

What scientists in various fields regard as the essence of theory thus corresponds, in fact, to the immediate tasks they set for themselves. The manipulation of physical nature and of specific economic and social mechanisms demand alike the amassing of a body of knowledge such as is supplied in an ordered set of hypotheses. [...] But the conception of theory was absolutized, as though it were grounded in the inner nature of knowledge as such or justified in some other ahistorical way, and thus it became a reified, ideological category.⁴⁶

Horkheimer's concern with methodological developments in theoretical philosophy and the philosophy of (social) science recalls Lukács' critique of the contemplative and reifying attitude typical of bourgeois science. Horkheimer dismisses traditional science as "the false consciousness of the bourgeois savant in the liberal era," because it approaches the "given world" as "a sum-total of facts" that "is there and must be accepted."⁴⁷ Like Lukács, he discusses how the positivistic example of the natural sciences becomes the scientific model for the human and social sciences, a theme that would remain paradigmatic within critical theory well into the second half of the twentieth century.⁴⁸

Critical theory, on the other hand, aims at the emancipation of humanity. Although Horkheimer shies away from specifying a fixed standpoint for social critique, he repeatedly refers to the omnipresence of suffering as the motivation for critical theory to reflect on the role of knowledge in reproducing the existing social order. Horkheimer suggests that social critique should question the injustice of suffering at a historical moment when "a community of free people" would be "possible through technical means already at hand."⁴⁹ At this inaugural moment, then, critical theory finds its firm grounding through partisanship with those who suffer unnecessarily, such that the mode of critique intrinsic to critical theory is "dominated at every turn by a concern for reasonable conditions of life."⁵⁰ Thus, Horkheimer premises the emancipatory commitment of critical theory on a rational critique of irrational social contradictions. He ascribes a "restricted rationality" to everyday facts as "the product of the activity of society as a whole," but questions the veracity of these facts by suggesting that reality is produced by the "blind result of conflicting forces," rather than the "conscious spontaneity of free individuals."⁵¹

Like Lukács, then, Horkheimer is concerned with the socialization of people into passive and contemplative participants to the capitalist form of life, who "see themselves only as onlookers, passive participants in a mighty process which may be foreseen but not modified" and who "simply accept the basic conditions of [their] existence as given and strive to fulfill them."⁵² Indeed, he discusses the formation of a type of subject reminiscent of Lukács' contemplative subject, who "finds satisfaction and praise in accomplishing as well as he [sic] can the tasks connected with his place in society and in courageously doing his duty."⁵³ Although Horkheimer does not explicitly use Lukács' notion of the contemplative attitude, the connection between his observations and Lukács' is hard to miss. For participants in capitalist societies, Horkheimer argues, "the present form of economy and the whole culture" is "their own world," which people "identify themselves with" and which they "conceive [...] as will and reason," while forgetting that it is not their own but the "world of capital," which is "supported by war and oppression" and is not the creation "of a unified, self-conscious will."⁵⁴

Moreover, Horkheimer explicitly uses the notion of a "critical attitude" as a counterpoint to the contemplative attitude towards society. In a passage

reminiscent of Foucault's use of the same term, he describes the critical attitude as being distrustful of the rules of conduct with which society as presently constituted provides each of its members. The separation between individual and society in virtue of which the individual accepts as natural the limits prescribed for his activity is relativized in critical theory."⁵⁵

However, Horkheimer's critical stance does not necessarily coincide with the perspective of the proletariat. Complicating Lukács' view, Horkheimer states that "the situation of the proletariat [...] is no guarantee of correct knowledge," because "this awareness is prevented from becoming a social force by the differentiation of social structure which is still imposed on the proletariat from above and by the opposition between personal class interests which is transcended only at very special moments."⁵⁶ The resulting position that Horkheimer envisions for critical theory is neither detached nor deeply rooted in existing social relations. As such, he introduces a role for the critical theorist that is antithetical to Lukács' standpoint-theoretical approach. He explicitly takes aim at Lukács' standpoint-theoretical hope, arguing that the intellectual should be "a critical, promotive factor in the development of the masses," rather than being "satisfied to proclaim with reverent admiration the creative strength of the proletariat and [find] satisfaction in adapting himself to it and in canonizing it."⁵⁷

Accordingly, Horkheimer adopts the position that would become typical of Frankfurt School critical theory, namely, that "the theoretician whose business it is to hasten developments which will lead to a society without injustice can find himself [sic] in opposition to views prevailing even among the proletariat."⁵⁸ The critical theorist sees themselves as a partisan of those who suffer, but claims for themselves a position from which a more correct view of society can be obtained than that emerging from below. Indeed, Horkheimer explicitly embraces the "conflict" between these points of view, arguing that without it "there would be no need of a theory; those who need it would come upon it without help."⁵⁹ As a result, the program of Frankfurt School critical theory is built on the assumption that the "inherent interest in the abolition of social injustice"⁶⁰ cannot take the viewpoints of those suffering injustice as its point of departure, but should start from the critical stance of the partisan theorists aiming at the abolition of social injustice.

III. FROM PESSIMISTIC TO TRANSCENDENTALIST CRITICAL THEORY

In his post-war collaboration with Adorno, Horkheimer becomes more explicitly pessimistic about the possibility of emancipatory politics. In 1968, he notes that "the idea of the growing wretchedness of the workers, out of which Marx saw rebellion and revolution emerging as a transitional step to the reign of freedom, has for long periods become abstract and illusory, and at least as out of date as the ideologies despised by the young."⁶¹ Despite efforts to find

optimism in the smallest instances that escape the total delusion of capitalism,⁶² Horkheimer's colleague Adorno often expresses himself in a similarly gloomy way. He argues that Marx and Engels mobilized historical materialism—with its occasional teleological overtones—as a strategic rather than teleological doctrine:

When Marx and Engels decided to translate even mankind's primal history, [...] into political economy [...] the motive that swayed them was the expectation of revolution as directly imminent. They wanted the revolution to come next day; hence their acute interest in breaking up trends that would, they had to fear, be crushed like Spartacus once upon a time, or like the peasant uprisings.⁶³

Adorno suggests that such strategic considerations would make no sense under late capitalist conditions. He argues that "Marx really did believe [...] that philosophers would in fact be best advised to pack it in and become revolutionaries, in other words, man the barricades."⁶⁴ According to Adorno, however, in post-war Germany, these barricades "cannot be found anywhere [...], and if they were to be erected in any advanced society today, they would be quickly eliminated by police or security guards."⁶⁵

As a result, Adorno and Horkheimer came to believe that critical theory could no longer be partisan in the sense of siding with concrete social struggles. Indeed, Adorno explains the shift from partisanship to pessimism in terms of the discrepancy between the development of the forces of production and the feasibility of emancipatory struggle. He claims that "what Marx regarded as the self-evident equivalence between the advances of the forces of production and the emancipation of mankind [sic] has ceased to hold good."⁶⁶ According to Honneth, "the nature of late-capitalist social systems" made it difficult for Adorno "to imagine an addressee for critical theory," replacing "the Marxian idea of a mass social movement [...] by the idea of an experience of oppression that can be formulated only on an individual basis."⁶⁷ With the failure of social revolutions, the rise of fascism, and the material and ideological integration of the working class, Adorno saw no other way but to return to philosophy, claiming that "philosophy, which once seemed obsolete, lives on because the moment to realize it was missed. [...] Having broken its pledge to be as one with reality or at the point of realization, philosophy is obliged ruthlessly to criticize itself."⁶⁸ At the same time, Adorno rejected a standpoint-theoretical ground for criticism altogether, suggesting that "in the end, glorification of splendid underdogs is nothing other than glorification of the splendid system that makes them so."⁶⁹ In sum, the partisan dimension of Frankfurt School critical theory faded after the Second World War because Adorno and Horkheimer saw no agent to side with. As Robin Celikates puts it, the Frankfurters "had to uphold the link to pre-theoretical experiences, oppositional forms of consciousness, and actually existing practices of critique and resistance, while, on the other hand, it became increasingly unclear how they were supposed to identify the social struggles and movements that their theory was meant to connect to and whether the conditions for them to emerge were given in the first place."⁷⁰

Abroad, however, the work of Herbert Marcuse provided a more optimistic counterpoint to the pessimism of Adorno and Horkheimer. Marcuse's entire project can be summarized as the search for a new revolutionary subject.⁷¹ Starting from his observation of "the prevalent integration of the working class into the capitalist system," he suggests that the consciousness of the working class might no longer manifest itself as "class" consciousness, but as "the consciousness of an opposition which expresses itself in new (or recaptured) modes of action," such as—and here Marcuse gives examples—"citizens' initiatives," "protest against nuclear energy installations," "against capitalist urban renewal," "the fight against racism and sexism," "the students' protest" and workers' "demands for the self-organization (autogestion) of work."⁷² Elsewhere, he argues that these group formations, whether within the militant intelligentsia of the middle class or the surplus populations on the margins of society, are "potential catalysts of rebellion within the majorities to which, by their class origin, they belong."⁷³ In other words, Marcuse seeks to channel the partisanship of critical theory into timely and concrete struggles and new social movements, suggesting that the challenge for critical theory is "articulating and winning over this large anti-capitalist (but not yet socialist) opposition" in order to reinvent the socialist project that his colleagues in Frankfurt had lost sight of.⁷⁴

Marcuse's partisan commitment to concrete social movements, however, proved not to be hegemonic within the Frankfurt School—nor did Foucault productively engage with his work.⁷⁵ While Marcuse sought to integrate the new social movements into Eurocommunism, Habermas was developing his theory of communicative action. Rather than prioritizing ongoing struggle, Habermas moved beyond the pessimism of his predecessors by developing an optimism about the collective learning processes implied by communicative action and the transcendental form of reason that secures it.⁷⁶ According to Habermas, it is possible to reconstruct communicative action as a capacity to question the reification that results from what he calls the colonization of the lifeworld. Indeed, he argues that "the theory of communicative action can ascertain for itself the rational content of anthropologically deep-seated structures by means of an analysis that, to begin with, proceeds reconstructively, that is, unhistorically."⁷⁷ Consequently, "theory must orient itself to the range of learning processes that is opened up at a given time by a historically attained level of learning" and "must refrain from critically evaluating and normatively ordering totalities, forms of life and cultures, and life-contexts and epochs as a whole."⁷⁸ Accordingly, Habermas redefines the task of critical theory as being the rational reconstruction of intersubjective communicative procedures to enable emancipatory interventions in capitalist societies. The task of critical theory, then, is not so much to exude a partisan commitment to social struggles; rather, Habermas' theory of communicative action tasks critical theory with "a critique of states of communication," insofar as they are under pressure due to their colonization by the system.⁷⁹ Thus, Habermas' reconstructive approach implies a normative and transcendental account of social critique. It aims to safe-

guard the normative structure of free argumentative exchange,⁸⁰ and presupposes that institutionalizing communicative action in modern democracies facilitates the procedures for “voluntarily associated free and equal citizens to legitimately regulate their collective lives through positive law.”⁸¹

His student Axel Honneth has criticized Habermas’s communi- cative paradigm by emphasizing that emancipatory concerns are not always expressed discursively. His emphasis on forms of non-verbal- ized feelings of misrecognition and disrespect restores the primacy of concrete struggles, although the stakes of Honneth’s theory of recogni- tion are also reconstructive rather than partisan. Honneth argues that, for critical theory, “the emotionally fired condemnation of disrespect and insult [...] represents an empirical interest which corresponds to the theoretical concerns of morality [...] capable of showing that moral progress is born of the struggle for recognition.”⁸² As such, his recog- nition-oriented paradigm relegates critique to assessing the extent to which struggles for recognition achieve the moral progress promised by the unfinished project of modernity. Critical theorists themselves, however, do not participate in the struggle for recognition, but take comfort in the idea that the institutional framework for such a struggle provides its conditions of possibility. Critical theory, for Honneth, is only concerned with outlining “how a moral culture could be so consti- tuted as to give those who are victimized, disrespected, and ostracized the individual strength to articulate their experiences in the democratic public sphere.”⁸³ As a result, Honneth turns out to see “conflict and struggle” as being “secondary with regard to the unfolding of institu- tionalized achievements and incremental learning processes,”⁸⁴ while at the same time reproducing the individualism of Adorno in a more optimistic framework.

In sum, efforts to revive the partisanship of critical theory following the postwar pessimism of Adorno and Horkheimer have taken Habermas’ transcendentalist road rather than Marcuse’s partisan road. The result is a return to a “traditional,” transcendental mode of critique that was criticized by Horkheimer and Lukács alike. Indeed, Whitebook notes that Habermas’ efforts to ground critique normatively had to “locate a standpoint outside the structure of systematically distorted communication.”⁸⁵ Whereas Lukács sought to ground the Archimedean point of critique in the (class) conflicts of capitalist society, post-Habermasian critical theory opts for a transcen- dental standpoint in an anthropologically deep-rooted and intersub- jective communicative rationality institutionalized by the procedures of post-traditional societies. As such, critical theory runs the risk to end up at the very point it initially critiqued: a transcendental theory that if purely formal and lacking in content, reifying the status quo it purportedly critiques.

Indeed, contemporary critical theorists inspired by feminism such as Lois McNay,⁸⁶ Amy Allen,⁸⁷ and Nancy Fraser,⁸⁸ have criticized the transcendentalization of the ground of emancipatory critique by pointing to its blind spot with respect to lived experiences as moments capable of motivating critique and political contestation. Their emphasis on the political thrust of

experiences of exclusion and subordination demonstrates their intention to give theoretical primacy to concrete struggle and resistance. But even the emphasis on lived experience does not develop a strategic and organizational partisanship with actual political struggle that exemplifies the Lukácsian roots of critical theory. If a partisan critical theory is to be redefined, it must go one step further and identify concrete struggles and subversive social practices for critical theory to adhere to, so as to ground critique's theoretical intentions.

IV. FOUCAULT, THE CRITICAL ATTITUDE, AND THE FRANKFURT SCHOOL

Habermas and Honneth locate the task of critical theory in the reconstruction of the context-transcending framework of justice and legitimation of post-traditional societies, rather than in the historically specific struggles of our time. They suggest that the existing rights and democratic institutions provide sufficient possibilities for countering the "colonization of the lifeworld," and for struggles to expand the scope of social recognition. Although Honneth has acknowledged that some of the institutions of liberal democracies to which his work adheres seem to have lost their emancipatory potential in the face of neoliberalism,⁸⁹ his work continues to uphold a post-revolutionary diagnosis of the present in which struggles can only make emancipatory gains through the institutions of modern liberalism.

Yet the recent return and popularity of "orthodox" critical theory seems to have arisen precisely because the normativism of Honneth and Habermas is unable to capture the struggles of our time.⁹⁰ In the remainder of this essay, I will argue that Foucault's work proposes an alternative to the solutions suggested by Honneth and Habermas in accounting for the changing forms of emancipatory struggles. Foucault's genealogical approach shares the challenge of rethinking the form that social emancipation might take following the material and ideological integration of the working class into capitalism. Hence, I suggest that Foucault's emphasis on the reciprocal relationship between power and resistance comes closer to the model of partisanship that characterizes Lukács' early work. As in the case of Lukács, I will show that Foucault approaches the possibility of undoing the self-evidence of hegemonic social formations by giving primacy to practices of resistance in the formation of a critical theory.

Before exploring these resonances, I should note an important difference between Foucault's approach and that of the Frankfurt School. Whereas Frankfurt School critical theory is explicitly committed to the idea of emancipation,⁹¹ Foucault is more skeptical about notions such as "liberation" and "emancipation."⁹² Foucault emphasizes that "there is no end point for struggles and resistance"⁹³ and argues that "if everything is dangerous [...] we always have something to do."⁹⁴ Elsewhere, he insists that there cannot be a society without power relations, and that the problem is "not to try to dissolve them in the utopia of completely transparent communication but to acquire the rules of law, the management techniques, and also the morality, the ethos, the

practice of the self, that will allow us to play these games of power with as little domination as possible.”⁹⁵

Moreover, Foucault does not assume the omnipresence of the commodity form,⁹⁶ as Lukács, Adorno, and Marcuse do.⁹⁷ In *The Birth of Biopolitics*, Foucault does make a similar observation, however, regarding the omnipresence of the market’s form as a generalized horizon organizing social life in neoliberal societies. He argues that “American neo-liberalism [...] involves, in fact, the generalization of the economic form of the market [...] throughout the social body and including the whole of the social system not usually conducted through or sanctioned by monetary exchanges.”⁹⁸ Although both Lukács and Foucault analyze how an economic form (“the commodity form,” “the market form”) is generalized, there are significant differences between their analyses. Most centrally, Foucault is interested in “the form of the market” as a technique of power that actively shapes society. Moreover, he explicitly claims that the neoliberal rationality of market competition is different from the logic of exchange central to Marxist analyses.⁹⁹ According to Lukács, on the other hand, the “commodity form” emerges from the tendencies of capitalism without any need for any active governmental intervention. Whereas Lukács suggests that the way subjectivities are shaped follows from the logic of capitalism itself, Foucault’s genealogy of the modern state addresses market competition as a principle created and introduced by the interventions of a governmental power.¹⁰⁰

Still, Foucault’s suggestion that the “political stake” of neoliberal governmentality “is quite simply the problem of the survival of capitalism, of the possibility and the field of possibilities still open for capitalism,”¹⁰¹ remains close to the Marx-inspired critique of capitalism typical of Lukács and the Frankfurt School. In fact, Foucault has claimed to have found his inspiration in the second volume of Marx’s *Capital*, rather than in the first volume’s analysis of commodity fetishism.¹⁰² In an interview from 1978, he asserts that what interests me about Marx, at least what I can say has inspired me, is Book 2 of *Capital*; that is to say everything that concerns the analyses of the genesis of capitalism, and not of capital, that are first of all historically concrete, and secondly the analyses of the historical conditions of the development of capitalism particularly on the side of the establishment, of the development of structures of power and of the institutions of power.¹⁰³

Placing emphasis on the “struggle” in class struggle, Foucault suggests that Marx’s political texts are more relevant to the project of critically analyzing power relations of his contemporary society than the analysis of the commodity form.¹⁰⁴

As we will see, for Foucault the analysis of power relations is inseparable from the fine-grained issues that resistance to these structures and institutions addresses.¹⁰⁵ I argue that Foucault’s power-theoretical approach gives primacy to concrete forms of struggle and resistance to locate the criteria for renouncing dominant forms of life and the regimes of power that maintain them. Foucault

observes that in Western societies in the post-revolutionary age of the twentieth century, political struggle emerges from social spheres beyond union bargaining and the vanguardism of traditional leftist organizations.¹⁰⁶ At the same time, he questions the emancipatory potential of a “sterile” reason such as Habermas’ communicative rationality.¹⁰⁷ Whereas Lukács increasingly moved from a Luxemburgian spontaneous approach to a Leninist vanguardism in response to the ideological crisis of the proletariat, Foucault made the reverse move: Rather than conceiving of vanguardist parties as vehicles of social change, he turned to a multiplicity of social struggles that contest a variety of seemingly self-evident—reified—forms of power and domination. Earlier in the 1970s, Foucault explicitly aligned himself with a non-vanguardist and coalitional left,¹⁰⁸ arguing that “most of the revolutionary movements that have developed recently in the world have been closer to Rosa Luxemburg than to Lenin” because “they place more trust in the spontaneity of the masses than in theoretical analysis.”¹⁰⁹ A few years later, however, Foucault would assert that the “death sentence for revolution seems [...] a little bit ridiculous,” precisely because “in all these struggles the point is the destabilization of the mechanisms of power, a destabilization apparently without end.”¹¹⁰ Accordingly, he comments favorably on social movements that revolve around “questions concerning daily life, sexual life, couples, women’s issues” and “problems of self-management” that seem “allergic to any party organization, incapable of finding its real expression in anything but groupuscules and individualities.”¹¹¹ Foucault’s focus on micropolitics, “anarchic” struggles, and groupuscules shows how the form of emancipatory struggle against the self-evidence of existing social relations has changed over the decades. In what follows, I explore Foucault’s perspective on the relationship between social critique and political practice.

According to Foucault, critique should problematize existing social norms and rationalities rather than provide utopian blueprints or develop normative claims about society.¹¹² Problematization-based critique involves questioning existing forms of life, and typically opposes the uncritical acceptance—or reification—of their inherent forms of power, knowledge, and subjectivity. In the first lecture of *The Government of Self and Others* (1982–83), Foucault argues that Kant’s text *Was ist Aufklärung* (1784) inaugurated a kind of philosophical inquiry typical of the modern critical attitude. There, he claims that Kant’s text on the Enlightenment targets the historical conditions of experience rather than their transcendental nature, as his *Critiques* do. Accordingly, Foucault suggests that the text introduces a historically specific form of philosophical critique of the “ontology of ‘ourselves’¹¹³—which he defines as the “cultural ensemble characteristic of [...] contemporary reality.”¹¹⁴

In the essays “What is Critique?” (1978) and “What is Enlightenment?” (1984), Foucault explicitly relates his problematization-based notion of critique to “the critical attitude.” He explains the emergence of the critical attitude from the strong link between science and the governmental power of the German state.¹¹⁵ In response, he suggests, it was up to philosophy to problematize the excesses of rationalization and its entanglement with power. He argues that “this

suspicion was especially well-developed [...] within what we could call the German Left,” which includes “the Frankfurt School” and its “critique of positivism, objectivism, rationalization, of technè and technicalization.”¹¹⁶ Since Foucault admits to having read Horkheimer’s early essays,¹¹⁷ he may have taken the term “critical attitude” from Horkheimer’s text. He locates his own project, along with that of the Frankfurt School, in a tradition that runs “from Hegel through Nietzsche or Max Weber to Horkheimer or Habermas.”¹¹⁸ Like Horkheimer, Foucault sees the critical theorist as “both an element and an actor”¹¹⁹ in the critique of society. In other words, the problematizing critique of the “ontology of ourselves” takes the form of an immanent critique of society, assuming that critique can only take the perspective of an insider in order to ask how things could be different.¹²⁰ By unearthing the relations of power working on subjective conduct and attitude, critique, for Foucault, aims at undoing the “self-evident, universal, and necessary” character¹²¹ of dominant forms of life.

As such, Foucault suggests that the critical attitude paves the way for “a critique of what we are saying, thinking, and doing through a historical ontology of ourselves.”¹²² This task corresponds to the paradigmatic task of critical theory, namely, to “separate out, from the contingency that has made us what we are, the possibility of no longer being, doing, or thinking what we are, do, or think.”¹²³ By addressing the contingent nature of the self-evident or seemingly necessary, Foucault also implies the possibility of transformative change. Moreover, the political significance of the critical attitude is to activate the tensions inherent in existing power relations. Indeed, Daniele Lorenzini has called Foucault’s method of critique “possibilizing” rather than problematizing, because it seeks to show that the critique of each power formation is always already contested by multiple forms of counter-conduct that are “‘normatively significant’ for us because they concretely embody the possibility of contesting existing forms of power.”¹²⁴

Following his belated acquaintance with the Frankfurt School,¹²⁵ Foucault continues to compare his mode of critique to theirs.¹²⁶ In an 1976 interview, he expresses his amazement that “the Frankfurt School passed by unnoticed for a long time in France,”¹²⁷ and articulates his appreciation of the Frankfurt School, which “tried ahead of time to assert things that I too had been working for years to sustain.”¹²⁸ Foucault’s superficial knowledge of German critical theory, however, led him to assume that the approaches within the Frankfurt School converged in the all-encompassing critique of “European rationality and its excesses”¹²⁹ which he considers to be “dangerous.”¹³⁰ Moreover, he claims that the proponents of Frankfurt School critical theory adopt the humanist concept of an original subject that is to be liberated, and criticizes the Frankfurt School’s overt focus on the excesses of a single rationality. He argues that his work, conversely, aims to uncover specific and diverse rationalities that are “grounded in a fundamental experience: madness, illness, death, crime, sexuality, etc.,”¹³¹ and “to discover which kind of rationality” is dominant in a given area of social life.¹³² To do this, Foucault suggests that critique must “refer to much more remote processes if we want to understand how we have been trapped in

our own history.”¹³³ Thus, genealogical critique does not focus on the excessive aspects of rationality itself, but rather on the historical conditions that allow the techniques of power to influence social life in such a way that its given form seems self-evident. Another reason to draw connections between Foucault and Lukács, then, is that whereas the first generation of the Frankfurt School increasingly focused on instrumental reason as such, Lukács’ critique of reification targets the specificities of a capitalist rationality that finds its central principle in the commodity form.

In sum, Foucault places his project close to the Frankfurt School, but also claims that it is “not ‘reason in general’ that is implemented, but always a very specific type of rationality.”¹³⁴ He concludes that the main goal of critique “is to attack not so much ‘such or such’ an institution of power, or group, or elite, or class but rather a technique, a form of power.”¹³⁵ In doing so, Foucault’s critical stance takes its impetus from efforts directed towards “how not to be governed like that, by that, in the name of those principles, with such and such an objective in mind and by means of such procedures, not like that, not for that, not by them.”¹³⁶ He therefore proposes his “very first definition of critique, this general characterization: the art of not being governed quite so much.”¹³⁷ The criteria permitting critique are thus, for Foucault, to be found in practices that resist the self-evidence of power. It is in relation to these practices of resistance that the critical attitude can become effective.

V. CRITIQUE, PRACTICE, AND PARTISANSHIP

As we have seen, for Foucault, the critical attitude constitutes “a way of limiting [...] arts of governing and sizing them up, transforming them, of finding a way to escape from them or, in any case, a way to displace them.”¹³⁸ Foucault argues that the question of power has traditionally been posed “only in terms of constitution, sovereignty” or “in terms of the state apparatus.”¹³⁹ He suggests that, during the twentieth century, a shift occurred towards the critique of the mesh of capillary forms of power. He argues that the kind of genealogical critique he proposes takes the lead from this shift, focusing on “the way power was exercised—concretely, and in detail—with its specificity, its techniques and tactics” which “could only begin after 1968 [...] on the basis of daily struggles at grass-roots level, among those whose fight was located in the fine meshes of the web of power.”¹⁴⁰ I suggest that Foucault’s critical project is partisan precisely because it gives concrete practices of resistance a leading role in his reflections on power.

As noted above, Foucault distanced himself from official party politics and engaged only selectively with political organizations such as trade unions,¹⁴¹ aligning himself with the Maoist and Trotskyist extra-parliamentary left, and later with the post-1968 social movements. The kinds of struggles to which critique can connect, according to Foucault, always have a “specific” and local character,¹⁴² precisely because they respond to specific relations of power. Indeed, Foucault considered himself a “specific intellectual,” rejecting the idea of a universal intellectual who speaks “in the capacity of master of truth and

justice,” who is “the consciousness/conscience of us all.”¹⁴³ According to Foucault, intellectuals working in “specific sectors” are able, because of their specific positionality, to gain “a much more immediate and concrete awareness of struggles,”¹⁴⁴ and to make relations of power “intelligible and therefore criticizable.”¹⁴⁵

Although many have presumed Foucault to be “inimical to large-scale political action,” convincing arguments have been made based on interviews and archival materials that Foucault’s work until the late 1970s can be understood as an effort “to defend a large-scale coalition politics outside the party form.¹⁴⁶ In fact, Foucault recommends that specific intellectuals simultaneously “operate and struggle at the general level.”¹⁴⁷ The role of the specific intellectual is to “try and isolate [...] the systems of thought that have become familiar to us, that appear self-evident and are integral with our perceptions, our attitudes, our behaviors.”¹⁴⁸ Consequently, Foucault even suggests that the specific intellectual is “drawn closer to the proletariat and the masses” because they are exposed to “real, material, everyday struggles” and confront “the same adversary as the proletariat, namely the multinational corporations, the judicial and police apparatuses.”¹⁴⁹

To emphasize the effects of such struggles, Foucault refers to “social movements” that “have really changed our whole lives, our mentality, our attitudes, and the attitudes and mentality of other people who do not belong to these movements.”¹⁵⁰ His approach to power as a social practice and relation suggests that resistance, whether in the form of explicit activism or more remote forms of counter-conduct, cannot be separated from the critique of power. Since power and resistance are in a reciprocal relationship, the critique of “not being governed that way” is immanent to ongoing struggles within society.¹⁵¹ It follows that in societies in which social change does not seem to be self-evident, the challenge for the theorist is to identify and engage with concrete practices that highlight the exercise of power. Indeed, in “The Subject and Power,” Foucault claims to take “the forms of resistance against different forms of power as a starting point [...], it consists in using this resistance as a chemical catalyst so as to bring to light power relations, locate their position, find out their point of application and the methods used.”¹⁵² Although Foucault is aware of power being a “reifying term,” his efforts, building upon concrete struggles, are directed towards developing “a critical investigation into the thematics of power.”¹⁵³ Indeed, Foucault admits that theory can only play a critical, subversive role insofar as it takes sides in ongoing struggles:

Perhaps philosophy can still play a role on the side of counter-power, on the condition [...] that philosophy stops thinking of itself as prophesy, [...] as pedagogy, or as legislation, and that it gives itself the task to analyse, clarify, and make visible, and thus intensify the struggles that develop around power, the strategies of the antagonists within relations of power, the tactics employed, the foyers of resistance ¹⁵⁴

Thus, Foucault invites us to combine social critique with a partisan concern for the social struggles around the forms of power being targeted.

In sum, Foucault argues that in the second half of twentieth century, political struggles took a different form from when revolutionary hope was still alive in Europe. Like his Frankfurt School colleagues, he observes that the material integration of the working class in post-industrial societies has diminished economic struggles, resulting in a changed form of social conflict. He claims that struggles over impoverishment may not be “completely solved,” but that they “no longer [have] the same urgency,” because they are “doubled by another problem that is not the problem of too little wealth, but rather that of too much power.”¹⁵⁵ Note that, like Adorno and Horkheimer, Foucault diagnoses late capitalism as a stage of material integration. In the early 1970s, Foucault was still emphasizing that with this changing form of social struggle “class struggle still exists, it exists more intensely.”¹⁵⁶ However, in the 1980s, he turned to workers’ unions to “counterbalance the state prerogative and to constitute counterpowers,” to “open up a space for innovation” on par with the changing form of resistance.¹⁵⁷ As such, his rejection of the Marxism of the French Communist Party did not follow from a rejection of all forms of politics related to class per se, but is rather characteristic of Foucault’s rejection of the parliamentarism of the PCF and its failure to adapt to the forms and variety taken by social struggles in society both within and beyond the scope of economic relations.¹⁵⁸ According to him, “political innovation, political creation, and political experimentation outside the great political parties,” meant that “people’s everyday lives have changed” because new “social movements have really changed our whole lives, our mentality, our attitudes, and the attitudes and mentality of other people who do not belong to these movements.”¹⁵⁹ Rather than suggesting that there are no longer any barricades, Foucault argues that “it is the questions of nurses or prison guards that interest—or should interest—intellectuals. [...] There is now a whole population that is becoming destabilized, that is moving, that is searching outside the habitual vocabularies and structures. It’s a... I dare not say cultural revolution, but certainly a cultural mobilization.”¹⁶⁰

CONCLUSION

Just as Frankfurt School critical theorists saw the problem of reification increasing after the Second World War, Foucault too understands the material integration of potentially subversive groups as the result of techniques of power aiming “to attenuate or to minimize a certain number of social conflicts,” leading to “the growing rigidity of certain mechanisms and the creation of situations of dependency.”¹⁶¹ Given this problem, Foucault’s emphasis on the primacy of struggle is of utmost importance: Where there is power, there is resistance—or, where there is reification, there is the objective possibility of social change—despite all the “ideological crises.” Like Lukács’ reflections on reification, Foucault, too, argues that “capitalism penetrates much more deeply into our existence.”¹⁶² Foucault’s work shows “that we can always rise up,” and tasks

critique “to multiply the occasions to rise up against the real that is given us.”¹⁶³ His suggestion that the “events of May 1968” display a “a whole series of questions that were not traditionally a part of its statutory domain [of politics]” carries much of the burden of proof for the development he recognized.¹⁶⁴ Foucault’s emphasis on actual struggles—“questions about women, about relations between the sexes, about medicine, about mental illness, about the environment, about minorities, about delinquency”¹⁶⁵—counteracts the artificial division between the “real” struggle of the working class and the supposedly reactionary politics of the lumpenproletariat and other marginalized social groups.¹⁶⁶ His involvement in social movements such as the Groupe d’Information sur les Prisons, the Groupe d’Information sur la Santé, as well as his support for the struggles of Solidarność, the feminist and gay movements, the liberation movements in Tunisia and Algeria, and his efforts to experiment with workers’ unions to find new forms of social security, all testify to an effort to redefine the partisanship of the intellectual beyond the parliamentarism of existing leftist strategies.¹⁶⁷ By identifying struggle, rather than theory, as leading the way in rejecting the current form of society, Foucault can be positioned close to the Lukácsian paradigm of social critique: The relevance of critical, rather than traditional theory lies precisely in self-reflexively engaging with moments of resistance in society in order to catalyze their struggles, insofar as an emancipatory moment can be made visible within them. Hence, critical theories should be mindful of the paradigmatic Lukácsian problem of political consciousness that accompanies the critique of reification, rationalization and power. My argument has been that Foucault’s work evidences such a “partisan” effort. Moreover, he reminds us “that there is always the possibility of changing. [...] If there was no resistance, there would be no power relations. Because it would simply be a matter of obedience. [...] So resistance comes first, and resistance remains superior to the forces of the process.”¹⁶⁸

Less obvious might be to point out the struggles of the working class “coming first,” as Lukács sought to do. Although Lukács gave the party a central role in organizing and mediating the consciousness of the proletariat, even his more Leninist essays suggest that the “the self-education of the proletariat” comes first.¹⁶⁹ Whereas Lukács still argued that questions of struggle were to be solved by the party “on the spur of the moment [...] on the basis of immediate expediencies,” which “are necessary in order to complete the revolutionary self-education of the proletariat,”¹⁷⁰ Foucault underlines that the form of such tactics changed beyond the party because “great new techniques of power (which correspond to multinational economies or bureaucratic states) must be opposed by new forms of politicization.”¹⁷¹ His shows that the challenge for critical theory is to decide which actors and struggles to side with, not because there are no longer any barricades, as Adorno assumed, but because their form is changing. Where Lukács wrote his standpoint theory in a situation of revolutionary class struggle, today, the critical theorist is invited to develop their interventions in partisanship with a wide variety of struggles: contesting the backlash against sexual minorities, people of color, migrants and refugees;

contesting the neoliberal marketization of social life; contesting the destruction of the earth and the environment; or contesting the far-right politics that diminish livability in all conceivable senses. Given today's diverse (but overlapping) political struggles, the partisanship of critique will necessarily be messier than before. Despite their diversity, I suggest that a better starting point for critical theories than transcendentalist paradigms would be to assess the critical quality of the interpretive, critical, and normative claims inherent to existing political struggles. In short, staying at the Grand Hotel Abyss will not change society. As such, the theorist must be "partisan" to intensify the struggles that are not the outcome of theoretical interpretation: they are the condition of critical theory.

NOTES

1. Michel Foucault, "Dialogue between Michel Foucault & Baqir Parham on Marx, Islam, Christianity & Revolution," *Daedalus* 134, no. 1 (2005): 366.
2. cf. Christian Voller, *In der Dämmerung: Vor- und Frühgeschichte der kritischen Theorie* (Matthes & Seitz Berlin, 2022).
3. Georg Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness: Studies in Marxist Dialectics* (MIT Press, 1971), 52; 79; 234; 327.
4. Martin Jay, "Ungrounded: Horkheimer and the Founding of the Frankfurt School," in *The Routledge Companion to the Frankfurt School*, ed. Peter E. Gordon, Espen Hammer, and Axel Honneth (Routledge, 2018), 138, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429443374>.
5. Of course, Adorno tried to maintain a unity between theory and praxis in his intellectual, philosophical and pedagogical endeavors. See Alex Demirović, *Der nonkonformistische Intellektuelle: von der kritischen Theorie zur Frankfurter Schule* (Mandelbaum, 2023).
6. Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary, s.v. "partisanship," accessed February 10, 2024, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/partisanship>.
7. Hauke Brunkhorst, "Paradigm-Core and Theory-Dynamics in Critical Social Theory: People and Programs," *Philosophy & Social Criticism* 24, no. 6 (November 1998): 77, <https://doi.org/10.1177/019145379802400604>.
8. Cf. Brunkhorst, "Paradigm-Core and Theory-Dynamics in Critical Social Theory"; Tivadar Vervoort, "Towards a Critique of Reification as a Critique of Forms of Life," *Metodo* 9, no. 2 (2021): 291-326, <https://doi.org/10.19079/metodo.9.2.291>.
9. For an exception, see Sakari Säynäjoki and Tuomo Tiisala, "Revisable A Priori as a Political Problem: Critique of Constitution in Critical Theory," *Journal of Social and Political Philosophy* 2, no. 2 (August 2023): 138-57, <https://doi.org/10.3366/jspp.2023.0054>.
10. Jürgen Habermas, *The Philosophical Discourse of Modernity: Twelve Lectures* (Polity Press, 2007), 280-81.

11. Gilles Deleuze, Foucault (University of Minnesota Press, 1988), 150f. Cf. Tivadar Vervoort, "Standpoint Theory and Foucauldian Genealogical Critique: Two Strategies for Mobilizing Situated Knowledge," *Hypatia* (forthcoming, 2025).
12. Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, *Collected Works*. 5 (International Publishers, 1843).
13. "The Intellectual Force of the 'Intellectual Workers,'" in *Tactics and Ethics* (Verso, 2014), 12.
14. *Tactics and Ethics* (London/New York: Verso, 2014), 35.
15. Tivadar Vervoort. "Towards a Critique of Reification as a Critique of Forms of Life," *Metodo* 9, no. 2 (2021): 291-326. <https://doi.org/10.19079/metodo.9.2.291>
16. Tivadar Vervoort, "'Nous Sommes Tous Néokantiens.' Foucault, Lukács and the Critique of Social Forms," *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science* 15, no 1 (2024): 209-241. <https://doi.org/10.1086/734638>
17. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein* (Luchterhand, 1977), 264; *History and Class Consciousness*, 89.
18. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 275; *History and Class Consciousness*, 100.
19. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 273; *History and Class Consciousness*, 99.
20. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 305; *History and Class Consciousness*, 126.
21. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 264; *History and Class Consciousness*, 89.
22. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 211; *History and Class Consciousness*, 38. All translations of *History and Class Consciousness* are adjusted by me.
23. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 252; *History and Class Consciousness*, 77.
24. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 111.
25. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 117.
26. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 141-42.
27. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 124.
28. cf. Rahel Jaeggi, "What (If Anything) Is Wrong with Capitalism? Dysfunctionality, Exploitation and Alienation: Three Approaches to the Critique of Capitalism," *The Southern Journal of Philosophy* 54 (September 2016): 44-65, <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjp.12188>.
29. *Geschichte und Klassenbewußtsein*, 393; *History and Class Consciousness*, 205.
30. Compare "The Marxism of Rosa Luxemburg" to "Critical Observations on Rosa Luxemburg's 'Critique of the Russian Revolution'" and "Towards a Methodology of the Problem of Organisation." Recently, Lauschke's book has lengthily discussed Lukács' meandering tour between Luxemburg and Lenin. Karl Lauschke, "Die Gegenwart als Werden erfassen": Inhalt, politischer Kontext und Rezeption von Georg Lukács' "Geschichte und Klassenbewusstsein" (Westfälisches Dampfboot, 2023).
31. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 320.
32. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 322.
33. Lukács, *Tactics and Ethics*, 1919-1929, 227-253.

34. John Clendaniel, "The Revolutionary Marxism of Lukács's Blum Theses," Lukács Archivum Nemzetközi Alapítvány, 2010, <https://www.lana.info.hu/lukacs-gyorgy/irasok-lukacsrol/john-clendaniel-the-revolutionary-marxism-of-lukacs-blum-theses/>; Lukács, *Tactics and Ethics, 1919-1929*.
35. György Lukács, "Gegen die Spontaneitätstheorie in der Literatur," *Linkskurve*, no.4 (April), 30-33. "Whoever attempts to replace Marxist criticism, which leads and guides, which analyzes false paths of the creative method and struggles for the correct creative method, with mass work is the literary-political equivalent of a Party member who would claim that the work of the central ideological and strategic leadership could be 'replaced' by spontaneous discussions in the factories." Russell Berman, "Lukács' Critique of Bredel and Ottwalt: A Political Account of an Aesthetic Debate of 1931-32," *New German Critique*, no. 10 (1977): 172, <https://doi.org/10.2307/487677>.
36. György Lukács, "'Tendency' or Partisanship?," in *Essays on Realism*, trans. Rodney Livingstone (MIT Press, 1981), 44.
37. Lukács, *Tactics and Ethics, 1919-1929*; cf. Lauschke, *Die Gegenwart als Werden erfassen*.
38. *History and Class Consciousness*, 299.
39. Lukács, "The Question of Parliamentarianism," in *Tactics and Ethics* (Verso, 2014), 55.
40. Lukács, "The Question of Parliamentarianism," 54.
41. cf. Voller, *In Der Dämmerung*.
42. Max Horkheimer, *Critical Theory: Selected Essays* (Continuum, 1982), 215.
43. Axel Honneth, "Moral Consciousness and Class Domination: Some Problems in the Analysis of Hidden Morality," *Praxis International* 1 (1982): 12.
44. Herbert Marcuse, "Philosophy and Critical Theory," in *Critical Theory and Society: A Reader*, ed. Stephen Eric Bronner and Douglas Kellner (Routledge, 1989), 63.
45. Marcuse, "Philosophy and Critical Theory," 197.
46. Marcuse, "Philosophy and Critical Theory," 192.
47. Marcuse, "Philosophy and Critical Theory," 199.
48. cf. H. P. Rickman and Theodor W. Adorno, "The Positivist Dispute in German Sociology," *The British Journal of Sociology* 27, no. 4 (December 1976): 509, <https://doi.org/10.2307/590190>.
49. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 327.
50. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 198-99.
51. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 200.
52. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 206.
53. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 206.
54. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 207.
55. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 206.
56. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 213.
57. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 214.

58. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 221.
59. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 221.
60. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, 242.
61. Horkheimer, *Critical Theory*, vi.
62. Cf. Theodor W. Adorno, *Minima Moralia: Reflections on a Damaged Life*, trans. E. F. N. Jephcott (Verso, 2005); Fabian Freyenhagen, *Adorno's Practical Philosophy: Living Less Wrongly* (Cambridge University Press, 2013); Peter Eli Gordon, *A Precarious Happiness: Adorno and the Sources of Normativity* (University of Chicago Press, 2023).
63. Theodor W. Adorno, *Negative Dialectics* (Taylor & Francis, 2004), 322.
64. Theodor W. Adorno, *Lectures on Negative Dialectics: Fragments of a Lecture Course 1965/1966* (Polity, 2008), 51.
65. Adorno, *Lectures*, 51.
66. Adorno, *Lectures*, 48.
67. Axel Honneth, "Communication and Reconciliation Habermas' Critique of Adorno," *Telos* 1979, no. 39 (April 1, 1979): 47, <https://doi.org/10.3817/0379039045>.
68. Adorno, *Negative Dialectics*, 3.
69. *Minima Moralia*, 28; Titus Stahl, "Intellectual Bad Conscience and Solidarity with the Underdogs," *Krisis | Journal for Contemporary Philosophy* 41, no. 2 (December 31, 2021): 67-69, <https://doi.org/10.21827/krisis.41.2.38070>.
70. Robin Celikates, "Critical Theory and the Unfinished Project of Mediating Theory and Practice," in *The Routledge Companion to the Frankfurt School*, ed. Peter E. Gordon, Espen Hammer, and Axel Honneth (Routledge, 2018), 2017, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429443374>.
71. Herbert Marcuse, *One-Dimensional Man: Studies in the Ideology of Advanced Industrial Society* (Routledge, 2002); cf. Herbert Marcuse, *An Essay on Liberation* (Beacon Press, 2000).
72. Herbert Marcuse, "The Reification of the Proletariat," in *Critical Theory and Society: A Reader*, ed. Stephen Eric Bronner and Douglas Kellner (Routledge, 1989), 290.
73. *An Essay on Liberation*, 51.
74. Marcuse, "The Reification of the Proletariat," 291.
75. Foucault's critique of the "repressive hypothesis" (cf. Michel Foucault, *The Will to Knowledge, The History of Sexuality* 1 (Penguin, 1998)) implicitly targets Marcuse's efforts to recast social struggle through the lens of the liberation of desires which, according to Marcuse, would motivate the anticapitalistic struggles of post-War Western societies. Some authors seek to argue that Foucault actually misreads Marcuse's argument and show parallels between their approaches. See Jeffrey Renaud, "Rethinking the Repressive Hypothesis: Foucault's Critique of Marcuse," *Symposium* 17, no. 2 (October 1, 2013): 76-93, <https://doi.org/10.5840/symposium201317221>; Joel Whitebook, "Michel Foucault: A Marcusean in Structuralist Clothing," *Thesis Eleven* 71, no. 1 (November 1, 2002): 52-70, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0725513602071011005>.

76. Seyla Benhabib, *Critique, Norm, and Utopia: A Study of the Foundations of Critical Theory* (Columbia University Press, 1986); Maeve Cooke, *Re-Presenting the Good Society* (MIT Press, 2006); Amy Allen, "The Unforced Force of the Better Argument: Reason and Power in Habermas' Political Theory," *Constellations* 19, no. 3 (September 2012): 353-68, <https://doi.org/10.1111/cons.12005>; Titus Stahl, "Habermas and the Project of Immanent Critique: Habermas and the Project of Immanent Critique," *Constellations* 20, no. 4 (December 2013): 533-52, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8675.12057>; Alex Demirovic, "Radical Democracy and Socialism," *Socialist Register* 54 (2018): 258-322.
77. Jürgen Habermas, "The Tasks of a Critical Theory of Society," in *Critical Theory and Society: A Reader*, ed. Stephen Eric Bronner and Douglas Kellner (Routledge, 1989), 296.
78. Habermas, "The Tasks of a Critical Theory of Society," 296.
79. Stefan Müller-Doohm, "Critical Theory," in *The Cambridge Habermas Lexicon*, ed. Amy Allen and Eduardo Mendieta, trans. Daniel Steuer (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 88, <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316771303.025>.
80. Jürgen Habermas, *The Theory of Communicative Action* (Beacon Press, 1984), I: 26.
81. James Gledhill, "The Ideal and Reality of Epistemic Proceduralism," *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy* 20, no. 4 (July 4, 2017): 489, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698230.2015.1033856>.
82. "Integrity and Disrespect: Principles of a Conception of Morality Based on a Theory of Recognition," in *The Fragmented World of the Social: Essays in Social and Political Philosophy* (SUNY Press, 1995), 260.
83. Axel Honneth, "The Social Dynamics of Disrespect: On the Location of Critical Theory Today," in *Disrespect: The Normative Foundations of Critical Theory* (Polity Press, 2007), 66.
84. Celikates, "Critical Theory and the Unfinished Project of Mediating Theory and Practice," 215.
85. Joel Whitebook, "Critical Theory And Psychoanalysis," in *The Routledge Companion to the Frankfurt School*, ed. Peter E. Gordon, Espen Hammer, and Axel Honneth (Routledge, 2018), 42, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429443374>.
86. "The Incompatibility of Formalism and Negativism," in *The Gender of Critical Theory*, by Lois McNay (Oxford University Press, 2022), 191-224, <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198857747.003.0007>.
87. *The End of Progress: Decolonizing the Normative Foundations of Critical Theory* (Columbia University Press, 2016).
88. "What's Critical about Critical Theory? The Case of Habermas and Gender," *New German Critique*, no. 35 (1985): 97-131, <https://doi.org/10.2307/488202>.
89. cf. Martin Hartmann and Axel Honneth, "Paradoxes of Capitalism," *Constellations* 13, no. 1 (2006): 41-58, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1351-0487.2006.00439.x>.

90. Peter E. Gordon et al., eds., “Max Horkheimer and the Foundations of the Frankfurt School,” in *The Routledge Companion to the Frankfurt School* (Routledge, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429443374>; Rahel Jaeggi, “Towards an Immanent Critique of Forms of Life,” *Raisons Politiques* 57, no. 1 (2015): 13, <https://doi.org/10.3917/rai.057.0013>; Jaeggi, “What (If Anything) Is Wrong with Capitalism? Dysfunctionalit, Exploitation and Alienation: Three Approaches to the Critique of Capitalism”; Titus Stahl, *Immanente Kritik: Elemente einer Theorie sozialer Praktiken* (Campus, 2013); Fabian Freyenhagen, “Was ist orthodoxe Kritische Theorie?,” *Deutsche Zeitschrift für Philosophie* 65, no. 3 (July 26, 2017): 456-69, <https://doi.org/10.1515/dzph-2017-0031>.
91. cf. Robin Celikates and Jeffrey Flynn, “Critical Theory (Frankfurt School),” in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, ed. Edward N. Zalta and Uri Nodelman (Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2023), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2023/entries/critical-theory/>.
92. cf. Michel Foucault, “Space, Knowledge, and Power,” in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1982; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 349-364; Michel Foucault, “On the Genealogy of Ethics: An Overview of Work in Progress,” in *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: Essential Works of Michel Foucault 1954-1984, Volume One* (1983; repr., Penguin Books, 2020).
93. Foucault, “On the Genealogy of Ethics: An Overview of Work in Progress,” 254.
94. Foucault, “On the Genealogy of Ethics,” 254.
95. Michel Foucault, “The Ethics of the Concern for Self as a Practice of Freedom,” in *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: Essential Works of Michel Foucault 1954-1984, Volume One*, ed. Paul Rabinow (1984; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 298.
96. cf. Michel Foucault, *The Birth of Biopolitics: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1978-79* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2008), 147-49; Michel Foucault et al., “Considerations on Marxism, Phenomenology and Power. Interview with Michel Foucault; Recorded on April 3rd, 1978,” *Foucault Studies*, September 14, 2012, 100, <https://doi.org/10.22439/fs.v0i14.3894>.
97. Werner Bonefeld and Chris O’Kane, eds., *Adorno and Marx: Negative Dialectics and the Critique of Political Economy* (Bloomsbury Academic, 2022). As Frank Engster puts it: “Critical Theory, in contrast, searches for the mediation between object-subject and their reciprocal constitution in the commodity-form and sphere of circulation” (Engster, 2018), 757.
98. Foucault, *The Birth of Biopolitics*, 243; my italics.
99. Foucault, 147; my italics. Foucault, 149. cf. Michel Foucault, “The Mesh of Power,” *Viewpoint Magazine*, September 12, 2012, <https://viewpointmag.com/2012/09/12/the-mesh-of-power/>; Michel Foucault, “Interview with Michel Foucault,” in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1980; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 284; Michel Foucault, *Society Must Be Defended: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1975-76*, 1st ed (Picador, 2003), 14; Deborah Cook, *Adorno, Foucault and the Critique of the West* (Verso, 2018), 31-61.

100. Nevertheless, Foucault does not understand the neoliberal regime as being enacted through some kind of subjective effort to consolidate its power. Instead, he suggests that “power relations are both intentional and nonsubjective” (1998, 94). It should be kept in mind, however, that in most Marxist approaches, economic relations of power are understood in the same way: the capitalist, for Marx is a “character mask” rather than a subjective and voluntary economic elite.
101. Foucault, *The Birth of Biopolitics*, 162.
102. As the first volume of *Capital* is published in two parts in French, it is unclear whether Foucault refers to the actual second volume, or part two of the first.
103. Foucault et al., “Considerations on Marxism, Phenomenology and Power. Interview with Michel Foucault; Recorded on April 3rd, 1978,” 100; cf. Gordon Hull, “How Foucault Got Rid of (Bossy) Marxism,” *Critical Review* 34, no. 3-4 (October 2, 2022): 372-403, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08913811.2022.2121516>.
104. Michel Foucault, “Entretien Inédit Entre Michel Foucault et Quatre Militants de La LCR,” *Rouge*, 1977; Michel Foucault, “Méthodologie pour la connaissance du monde,” in *Dits et écrits: 1954 - 1988*. 3: 1976-1979 (1978; repr., Gallimard, 1994), 612; Michel Foucault, “The End of the Monarchy of Sex,” in *Foucault Live: Interviews, 1961-1984*, ed. Sylvère Lotringer (1977; repr., Semiotexte, 1996), 225.
105. Foucault’s positioning in relation to Marxism has prompted the critique that he would have favored a market-based liberalism. The authors of *Foucault and Neoliberalism: The Last Man Takes LSD*, for example, argue that Foucault was The First Man to like neoliberalism. Despite the tendentious nature of Daniel Zamora and Mitchell Dean’s intervention, their interpretation of Foucault’s attitude towards neoliberalism can be summed up in one (admittedly long) sentence. They claim that Foucault’s personal experiments with sex and drugs, as well as his resentment of the socialist movement in France, convinced him that politics should not revolve around the seizure of state power through class-based mass politics, but should be oriented toward experimentation with the self, for which the environmental power techniques of neoliberal governmentality would provide fertile ground. Or, as Dean and Zamora themselves put it: “since the revolution was no longer desirable, Foucault thought that a new kind of politics should be invented that would open the way for a Left that no longer rejected the market and could therefore create a space free both from the state and from the normativity of the ‘social-statist’ governmentality,” a space for which “Foucault discovered in neoliberalism a fascinating framework.” Mitchell Dean and Daniel Zamora, *The Last Man Takes LSD: Foucault and the End of Revolution* (Verso, 2021), 71. If we look more closely at Foucault’s explicit engagement with politics, however, he argues that theorists should orient themselves towards everyday struggles against all forms of (governmental) power, including neoliberal governmentality. Michel Foucault, “Sei to seiji wo Kataru (‘Sexualité et politique’),” in *Dits et écrits: 1954-1988*. 3: 1976-1979 (1978; repr., Gallimard, 1994), 522-32.

106. cf. "Structuralism and Post-Structuralism," in *Aesthetics, Method, and Epistemology: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-1984, Volume Two* (1983; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 454-55; Foucault, "Interview with Michel Foucault," 288; Michel Foucault, "The Analytic Philosophy of Politics," trans. Giovanni Mascaretti, *Foucault Studies*, June 29, 2018, 188-200, <https://doi.org/10.22439/fs.v0i24.5532>.
107. Michel Foucault, "'Omnes et Singulatim': Towards a Critique of Political Reason," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1981; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 328; Foucault, "Space, Knowledge, and Power," 357; Foucault, "Structuralism and Post-Structuralism"; Foucault, "The Ethics of the Concern for Self as a Practice of Freedom," 298.
108. Luke Ilott, "Genealogy Beyond Critique: Foucault's Discipline and Punish as Coalitional Worldmaking," *Political Theory*, July 5, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00905917221103296>; Luke Ilott, "Generalizing Resistance: The Coalition Politics of Foucault's Governmentality Lectures," *The Review of Politics*, October 4, 2022, 1-25, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0034670522000882>.
109. "Return to History," in *Aesthetics, Method, and Epistemology: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-1984, Volume Two* (1972; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 422-23.
110. Foucault, "The Analytic Philosophy of Politics," 197.
111. "Structuralism and Post-Structuralism," 453-54.
112. Michel Foucault, "Polemics, Politics, and Problematizations," in *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: Essential Works of Michel Foucault 1954-1984, Volume One* (1984; repr., Penguin Books, 2020); Michel Foucault, "What Is Enlightenment?," in *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: Essential Works of Michel Foucault 1954-1984, Volume One* (1984; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 309; Colin Koopman, *Genealogy as Critique: Foucault and the Problems of Modernity* (Indiana University Press, 2013); Amy Allen, "Foucault and Enlightenment: A Critical Reappraisal," *Constellations* 10, no. 2 (June 2003): 180-98, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8675.00323>; Daniele Lorenzini, "On Possibilising Genealogy," *Inquiry*, January 9, 2020, 1-22, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020174X.2020.1712227>.
113. Michel Foucault, *The Government of Self and Others: Lectures at the Collège de France 1982-1983* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), 20.
114. Foucault, *The Government of Self and Others*, 13.
115. cf. Michel Foucault, "Introduction," in *The Normal and the Pathological*, by Georges Canguilhem (1977; repr., Zone Books, 1989), 7-24.
116. "What Is Critique?," in *The Politics of Truth*, ed. Sylvère Lotringer (1978; repr., Semiotext(e), 2007), 51.
117. cf. *Remarks on Marx: Conversations with Duccio Trombadori*, ed. Duccio Trombadori, trans. R. James Goldstein and James Cascaito (1980; repr., Autonomedia, 1991), 116; *The Birth of Biopolitics*, 105.

118. "What Is Enlightenment?," 303. Foucault also took note of Kirchheimer's work on punishment (cf. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison* (Vintage, 2012), 24; 54; *Remarks on Marx*, 116; "Questions of Method," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1980; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 223-38.), texts on libidinal liberation (cf. *Society Must Be Defended*, 5.) the critique of liberalism by Marcuse (*The Birth of Biopolitics*, 117; cf. *Security, Territory, Population: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1977-78* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 338.), and some facets of Habermas' thought (Foucault, "What Is Enlightenment?"; Michel Foucault, "Sexuality and Solitude," in *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: Essential Works of Michel Foucault 1954-1984, Volume One* (1981; repr., Penguin Books, 2020).).
119. *The Government of Self and Others: Lectures at the Collège de France 1982-1983*, 12.
120. cf. Stahl, *Immanente Kritik*; Rahel Jaeggi, "Rethinking Ideology," in *New Waves in Political Philosophy*, ed. Boudewijn de Bruin and Christopher F. Zurn (Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 63-86, https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230234994_4; Jaeggi, "Towards an Immanent Critique of Forms of Life."
121. Foucault, "Questions of Method," 227.
122. "What Is Enlightenment?," 315; cf. Michel Foucault, "The Political Technology of Individuals," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1988; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 403. "What Is Enlightenment?," 309.
123. Foucault, "What Is Enlightenment?," 315-16.
124. Lorenzini, "On Possibilising Genealogy," 3.
125. Foucault, "Structuralism and Post-Structuralism," 440.
126. *The Government of Self and Others: Lectures at the Collège de France 1982-1983*, 20-21; cf. Michel Foucault, "Life: Experience and Science," in *Aesthetics, Method, and Epistemology: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-1984, Volume Two* (1985; repr., Penguin Books, 2020).
127. Foucault, *Remarks on Marx*, 116.
128. Foucault, *Remarks on Marx*, 117.
129. "'Omnes et Singulatim': Towards a Critique of Political Reason," 328; *The Birth of Biopolitics*, 36.
130. cf. Foucault, "Questions of Method," 229.
131. "'Omnes et Singulatim': Towards a Critique of Political Reason," 328.
132. "Truth and Juridical Forms," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954- 84, Volume Three* (1974; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 1; cf. "The Subject and Power," *Critical Inquiry* 8, no. 4 (1982): 779, <https://doi.org/10.1086/448181>; *The Birth of Biopolitics*, 36.
133. "'Omnes et Singulatim': Towards a Critique of Political Reason," 300.
134. Foucault, *The Birth of Biopolitics*, 242.
135. Foucault, "The Subject and Power," 781.
136. Foucault, "What Is Critique?," 44.
137. Foucault, "What Is Critique?," 44.
138. Foucault, "What Is Critique?," 44.

139. Michel Foucault, "Truth and Power," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1977; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 117.
140. Foucault, "Truth and Power," 117.
141. Frédéric Lebaron, "Michel Foucault: de la critique de l'économie à l'action syndicale," in *L'infréquentable Michel Foucault*, ed. Didier Eribon (EPEL, 2001), 157-67; Foucault, "Entretien Inédit Entre Michel Foucault et Quatre Militants de La LCR"; Foucault et al., "Considerations on Marxism, Phenomenology and Power. Interview with Michel Foucault; Recorded on April 3rd, 1978"; Michel Foucault, "A Last Interview with Michel Foucault," *City Paper* 8, no. 30 (August 27, 1984): 18; John K. Simon and Michel Foucault, "A Conversation with Michel Foucault," *Partisan Review* 38 (1971): 92-210; Michel Foucault, "Interview with Actes," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1984; repr., Penguin Books, 2020); Michel Foucault, "Sex, Power, and the Politics of Identity," in *Ethics, Subjectivity, and Truth: Essential Works of Michel Foucault 1954- 1984, Volume One* (1984; repr., Penguin Books, 2020).
142. Foucault, "Truth and Power."
143. Foucault, "Truth and Power," 126.
144. Foucault, "Truth and Power," 126.
145. Michel Foucault and Lawrence D. Kritzman, *Politics, Philosophy, Culture: Interviews and Other Writings, 1977-1984* (Routledge, 1988), 125.
146. Ilott, "Generalizing Resistance," 1-4; cf. Ilott, "Genealogy Beyond Critique"; Hull, "How Foucault Got Rid of (Bossy) Marxism." As Ilott concludes, "Foucault conceived his work as contributing to the "future formation of a 'we,'" fostering a "community of action" ([1984c] 2020). Like his Gramscian contemporaries, he affirmed the need for oppositional forces to form alliances and, in rare cases, constitute a unified "collective will" capable of large-scale transformations beyond the merely local level ([1977] 2005, 134). But unlike Gramsci, Foucault did not conceive the political party as the nucleus of this will. His vision of alliance politics was not about gathering multiple agents into a single organizational hierarchy, but about ushering distinct, parallel movements towards common targets, combining their strength without diminishing their autonomy" (Ilott 2022b, 25).
147. Foucault, "Truth and Power," 131-32.
148. "What Is Called 'Punishing'?", in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954- 84, Volume Three* (1984; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 384.
149. Foucault, "Truth and Power," 126.
150. Foucault, "Sex, Power, and the Politics of Identity," 173.
151. Foucault, *The Will to Knowledge*; Foucault, *Security, Territory, Population: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1977-78*; Foucault, "The Subject and Power."
152. Foucault, "The Subject and Power," 781.
153. Foucault, "The Subject and Power," 786.
154. Foucault, "The Analytic Philosophy of Politics," 192.

155. Foucault, "The Analytic Philosophy of Politics," 189.
156. Simon and Foucault, "A Conversation with Michel Foucault," 198.
157. Foucault, "The Risks of Security," in *Power: Essential Works of Foucault 1954-84, Volume Three* (1983; repr., Penguin Books, 2020), 371.
158. Simon and Foucault, "A Conversation with Michel Foucault," 201.
159. Foucault, "Sex, Power, and the Politics of Identity," 172-73.
160. Michel Foucault, "Une mobilisation culturelle," in *Dits et écrits: 1954 - 1988. 3: 1976-1979* (1977; repr., Gallimard, 1994), 330; my translation.
161. Foucault, "The Risks of Security," 366.
162. Foucault, "Truth and Juridical Forms," 86.
163. Michel Foucault and Farés Sassine, "There Can't Be Societies without Uprisings," trans. Alex Feldman, *Foucault Studies*, October 22, 2018, 343, <https://doi.org/10.22439/fs.v0i25.5588>.
164. Foucault, "Polemics, Politics, and Problematizations," 115.
165. Foucault, "Polemics, Politics, and Problematizations," 115.
166. "Interview with Jean François and John De Wit," in *Wrong-Doing, Truth-Telling: The Function of Avowal in Justice*, ed. Fabienne Brion, Bernard E. Harcourt, and Stephen W. Sawyer (1981; repr., University of Chicago Press, 2014), 262, <https://www.bibliovault.org/BV.landing.epl?ISBN=9780226922089>.
167. Foucault, "The Risks of Security," 366.
168. Foucault, "Sex, Power, and the Politics of Identity," 168.
169. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 264.
170. Lukács, *History and Class Consciousness*, 264.
171. Michel Foucault, "Power Affects the Body," in *Foucault Live: Interviews, 1961 - 1984*, ed. Sylvère Lotringer (1976; repr., Semiotexte, 1996), 211.